

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14888940>

A CASE STUDY AND A CONCISE ACCOUNT OF RIEDEL'S THYROIDITIS

Scientific supervisor: PhD. Docent **Negmatova Gulzoda Shukhratovna**

Head of the Department of Endocrinology, Samarkand State Medical University

¹ **Abdiyev Lazizbek**

² **Ibragimov Kamronbek**

Clinical residents specializing in endocrinology,
Samarkand State Medical University

Annotation. *Riedel's thyroiditis (fibroinvasive thyroiditis) is a rare form of chronic inflammatory disease of the thyroid gland, characterized by progressive replacement of glandular tissue with fibrous tissue with spread into the capsule and surrounding tissues. The disease can lead to compression symptoms, such as difficulty breathing, pain when swallowing and compression of blood vessels and trachea. Diagnosis is based on clinical data and the results of instrumental studies, such as ultrasound (hypoechoic areas), scintigraphy, CT and MRI, as well as elastography, showing tissue rigidity. Riedel's thyroiditis is often associated with fibrosis of other organs (orbits, mediastinum, retroperitoneal space) and can be associated with IgG4-mediated inflammation, but an increase in IgG4 levels in the blood is not always observed. Despite the rarity of the disease, it represents a significant diagnostic and therapeutic problem, especially in the case of complications associated with compression of vital structures. The article discusses the clinical features, diagnostic methods and modern approaches to the treatment of Riedel's thyroiditis, as well as possible associations with other fibrosing diseases.*

Keywords: *Riedel's thyroiditis, fibro-invasive thyroiditis, thyroid gland, fibrosis, compression syndrome, hypothyroidism, ultrasound, scintigraphy, CT, MRI, elastography, IgG4, inflammation, diagnostics, fibrosis, neck organs, multifocal fibrosclerosis.*

INTRODUCTION. Riedel's thyroiditis is a rare disease in which inflammation of the thyroid gland leads to the replacement of normal tissue of the gland with fibrous tissue. This process can spread to the capsule of the gland and neighboring organs,

creating risks of compression of blood vessels, trachea and other structures of the neck. This, in turn, can cause symptoms such as difficulty breathing, pain when swallowing and a feeling of pressure in the neck. The disease develops slowly, and in the early stages, symptoms may be barely noticeable. If only one lobe of the thyroid gland is affected, hormonal levels may remain normal, but if fibrosis affects the entire gland, hypothyroidism occurs. Palpation is used to diagnose the disease (the thyroid gland becomes dense and slightly mobile), ultrasound (where areas with low echogenicity and poor blood supply are visible), as well as scintigraphy, CT or MRI, which can show the spread of fibrosis to other tissues and organs. PET scanning may be useful in identifying areas of fibrosis and in monitoring disease dynamics after treatment. In some cases, a decrease in fluorine-18-fluorodeoxyglucose uptake is associated with improvement in symptoms, but this is not always the case. Fine-needle biopsy (FNB) of the thyroid gland in Riedel's thyroiditis is often non-diagnostic, but in some cases, fibrous tissue fragments and signs of inflammation may be found. The diagnosis is usually made after thyroid surgery, when symptoms of compression occur. Histological examination shows dense hyalinized tissue with sparse colloid and a characteristic eosinophilic infiltrate. Morphological and immunohistochemical studies are necessary to confirm the diagnosis. It is important to exclude malignancies, giant cells, lymphoid follicles, oncocytes, and granulomas. The use of blood IgG4 levels and immunohistochemistry for diagnosis remains an open question, since elevated IgG4 is not always present. It is important to differentiate autoimmune thyroiditis (eg, Hashimoto's thyroiditis) and malignancies. Complications of Riedel's thyroiditis may include extension of fibrosis to adjacent organs, tracheal stenosis, occlusion of neck vessels, and involvement of the sympathetic nerve trunk. This may lead to dyspnea, venous thrombosis, and Horner's syndrome. In 14% of cases, the parathyroid glands are involved, causing hypoparathyroidism. Treatment of Riedel's thyroiditis usually includes glucocorticosteroids to reduce inflammation. If these are ineffective, tamoxifen may be prescribed, which helps modulate the inflammatory process. In cases of treatment refractoryness, rituximab or a combination of prednisolone and mycophenolate mofetil may be used. If the symptoms of compression do not go away after drug therapy, surgical intervention is indicated. However, surgery can be difficult due to dense tissue infiltration, and in such cases limited surgeries such as isthmus dissection or hemithyroidectomy are often performed to relieve the symptoms of compression.

CLINICAL CASE. Patient A., 42 years old, was admitted to the Surgery Department of the Sverdlovsk Federal Scientific and Pedagogical Center of Epidemiology and Epidemiology in July 2024 with complaints of a feeling of persistent

suffocation and discomfort in the neck. Upon admission to the department, the patient's condition was satisfactory, blood pressure 120/90 mm Hg, heart rate 80 beats/min, temperature 36.6 °C. Upon examination, the isthmus and left lobe of the thyroid gland are enlarged, dense, painless on palpation. Hereditary history: no thyroid diseases in relatives. Bad habits: smoking - 1 pack of cigarettes per day. It is known from the anamnesis that in September 2023 (at the age of 44), the patient noted an increase in the size of the neck, an increase in body temperature to 38 °C after an infection. She was diagnosed with ARVI, and received symptomatic treatment. During examination at the place of residence (end of September 2023), an ultrasound scan of the thyroid gland revealed a 5 cm nodular formation, the total volume of the thyroid gland was not described. Fine-needle aspiration biopsy was performed, a cytological conclusion was obtained: the preparation is abundantly cellular, fibrin threads, lymphocytes, colloid, groups of thyroid epithelial cells with proliferation, TIRADS II are present. The TSH level at the time of application was 2.3 mIU / l, AT-TPO increased to 528 IU / ml. Then, in December 2023, due to an increase in the feeling of suffocation, hoarseness, and increased discomfort in the neck, a decision was made at the place of residence to perform a subtotal resection of the thyroid gland on the left. According to histology: a morphological picture corresponding to Riedel's fibrous thyroiditis. After the surgery, the patient's condition temporarily improved: the feeling of suffocation and hoarseness decreased. However, due to the progression of the disease (enlargement of the thyroid gland, increasing discomfort, the feeling of suffocation, hoarseness) and the histological examination of TR, prednisolone was prescribed at a dose of 80 mg / day since February 2024. Against the background of the therapy, positive dynamics were noted with a decrease in the feeling of suffocation and discomfort. In April 2024, due to the development of clinical signs of exogenous hypercorticism (manifested by matronism, weight gain, uneven distribution of subcutaneous fat), the dose of prednisolone was reduced to 65 mg / day. In dynamics (end of April 2024) according to ultrasound data: the total volume of the thyroid gland was 50 ml, in the right lobe there was a formation in a calcified capsule measuring 0.7 x 0.6 x 0.7 cm, an isoechoic formation of mixed structure measuring 1.1 x 1.1 x 0.9 cm. In blood tests from April 2024: TSH 1.3 mIU / l, C-reactive protein 0.28 mg / l, ESR 8 mm / h. In all finished preparations, a histological picture corresponding to Riedel's fibrous thyroiditis was found. At the time of admission, she was taking prednisolone 10 mg / day, pantoprazole 80 mg / day, calcium carbonate 1000 mg / day. Results of physical, laboratory and instrumental studies. The following results were obtained during this hospitalization: TSH 0.929 mIU/L, calcitonin less than 1.00 pg/ml (0–4.8), parathyroid hormone 50.6 pg/ml (15–65 pg/ml), total calcium 2.47 mmol/l (2.15–2.55 mmol/l), phosphorus 1.25 mmol/l (0.74–1.52 mmol/l), C-reactive protein 5.8 mg/l. Thyroid ultrasound was

performed: the contours of the gland are smooth, unclear, the gland is low-lying, it embraces the trachea without narrowing it, it deforms the contours of the esophagus, the pretracheal muscles on the left and in the isthmus area are edematous, the border between them and the capsule of the gland is blurred. Vascularization during color Doppler imaging is unchanged. Echogenicity is moderately reduced on the left and in the isthmus area with a transition to the right lobe. Also in the right lobe there were nodular formations: 0.9 cm with calcifications in the capsule, 0.6-0.7 cm of average echogenicity (TIRADS 2). In the left lobe near the isthmus there is a hypoechoic zone of 0.5 cm with small calcifications (TIRADS 4a). The total volume of the thyroid gland is 48.9 cm³. According to CT of the neck it was revealed that the altered left lobe is adjacent to the internal jugular vein without narrowing of its lumen, adjacent to the common carotid artery (fatty tissue between them is preserved). Anteriorly, the gland is adjacent to the sternohyoid/sternothyroid muscles. The muscles are poorly differentiated (their involvement cannot be excluded). Compression syndrome was not revealed. During CT of the neck, attention was drawn to the detection of a partially floating thrombus in the right internal jugular vein, thromboembolism of the left pulmonary artery and its branches. However, given the stable condition, the absence of respiratory failure, and the absence of changes in the lung tissue during chest CT, acute massive PE was excluded. Given the CT picture of the floating thrombus, as well as CT signs of thromboembolism of the left pulmonary artery, the patient was prescribed oral anticoagulant therapy. The presence of a partially floating thrombus in the right internal jugular vein is most likely associated with damage to the intima of the vessel during thyroid surgery in December 2023. An examination was performed for the presence of systemic fibrosing disease. CT of the chest and mediastinal organs did not reveal focal or infiltrative changes. Examination of the abdominal organs did not reveal data for sclerosing cholangitis. Based on the results of the ophthalmologist consultation, no data were received for orbital fibrosis, the diagnosis was: OU - Mild myopia, retinal angiopathy. To exclude IgG4-associated disease, IgG and IgG4 were determined, the results revealed normal levels of these parameters (IgG 6.5 g/l (7.0–16.0), IgG4 0.057 g/l (less than 2.01)), which excluded IgG4-associated disease. Based on laboratory and instrumental research methods, the effectiveness of the glucocorticosteroid therapy was confirmed: a decrease in the goiter size and the absence of compression symptoms were noted. Thus, it was recommended to take prednisolone at a maintenance dose of 10 mg under the control of the patient's well-being, thyroid ultrasound. Outcome and results of follow-up. According to dynamic control data: for another 6 months. The patient continued taking glucocorticosteroids with subsequent gradual withdrawal of the drug. No compression symptoms were noted against the background of withdrawal.

CONCLUSION. There are currently no standard protocols for the treatment of such patients, and in some cases, TR can progress rapidly. However, when conducting imaging studies, it is important to consider the characteristics of fibrotic thyroid disease in TR. One of the key diagnostic steps is to determine the levels of IgG and IgG4 to exclude IgG4-associated disease. Treatment of TR should be individualized and require the participation of several specialists. In this case, the diagnosis was established based on the results of histological examination after surgery. However, after surgery, the patient's condition worsened, and prednisolone was prescribed, which gave a positive effect. At the same time, with this dose of prednisolone, signs of hypercorticism were noted, which required a reduction in the dose of the drug. Subsequently, against the background of long-term use of 10 mg of prednisolone, the condition stabilized.

References:

1. Кадирова А, Юсупов А, Бобоев С. Интраокулярная коррекция миопии высокой степени. *Каталог монографий*. 2023;(1):1-104.
2. Юсупов АА, Хамракулов СБ, Бобоев СА. КОРРЕКЦИЯ ВРОЖДЕННОЙ АНИЗОМЕТРОПИЧЕСКОЙ МИОПИИ ВЫСОКОЙ СТЕПЕНИ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ФАКИЧНЫХ ИНТРАОКУЛЯРНЫХ ЛИНЗ. *Advanced Ophthalmology*. 2023;1(1):187-190. doi:10.57231/j.ao.2023.1.1.044
3. Абдурахманович БС, Абдуазизович ЮА. МИКРОИМПУЛЬСНАЯ ЛАЗЕРНАЯ ЦИКЛОФОТОКОАГУЛЯЦИЯ В ЛЕЧЕНИИ РЕФРАКТЕРНОЙ ГЛАУКОМЫ. *Advanced Ophthalmology*. Published online April 19, 2023. Accessed February 2, 2025. <https://journals.scinnovations.uz/index.php/ao/article/view/536>
4. А.т А, Ж.а Р, А.а Ю, И.н Я. ОЦЕНКА ЭПИДЕМИОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ СИТУАЦИИ С ДИАБЕТИЧЕСКОЙ РЕТИНОПАТИЕЙ В ГОРОДЕ САМАРКАНД. *Экономика и социум*. 2024;(4-1 (119)):758-761.
5. Бабаев СА, Кадирова АМ, Хамракулов СБ. ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ЗАДНЕКАМЕРНЫХ ФАКИЧНЫХ ИОЛ ПРИ КОРРЕКЦИИ МИОПИИ ВЫСОКОЙ СТЕПЕНИ. *GOLDEN BRAIN*. 2024;2(1):329-335.
6. Абдурахманович БС, Муратовна КА. РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ЛЕНСЭКТОМИИ В ЛЕЧЕНИИ БОЛЬНЫХ С ПЕРВИЧНОЙ ЗАКРЫТОУГОЛЬНОЙ ГЛАУКОМОЙ. *Advanced Ophthalmology*. Published online April 19, 2023. Accessed February 2, 2025. <https://journals.scinnovations.uz/index.php/ao/article/view/535>

7. З ЖД, А БС. РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ОЦЕНКИ УРОВНЯ ЭНДОТЕЛИНА-1 И Д-ДИМЕРОВ В СЛЕЗНОЙ ЖИДКОСТИ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С АРТЕРИАЛЬНОЙ ГИПЕРТЕНЗИЕЙ. *SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF APPLIED AND MEDICAL SCIENCES*. 2024;3(3):300-307.
8. З ЖД, А БС. РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ОЦЕНКИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ КОМПЛЕКСНОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С 3-4 СТАДИЯМИ ГИПЕРТОНИЧЕСКОЙ АНГИОРЕТИНОПАТИИ. *SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF APPLIED AND MEDICAL SCIENCES*. 2024;3(3):308-315.
9. Юсупов А, Василенко А, Юсупова Н. Результаты хирургической коррекции высокой анизометропии у больных с косоглазием. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2018;(4 (104)):135-136.
10. Жалалова Д, Норматова Н, Бобоев С. Фенофибраты в лечении диабетической офтальмопатии. *Каталог монографий*. 2023;(1):2-120.
11. Косимов РЭ, Бобоев СА, Кадирова АМ. ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОЕ ЛЕЧЕНИЕ ВТОРИЧНОГО РАСХОДЯЩЕГОСЯ КОСОГЛАЗИЯ У ДЕТЕЙ. *Advanced Ophthalmology*. 2023;1(1):128-131. doi:10.57231/j.ao.2023.1.1.030
12. Abdurakhmanovich BS, Botirovich KS, Sadullaevich RS. CORRECTION OF ANISOMETROPIA BY PHAKIC INTRAOCULAR LENSES IN PATIENTS WITH CONGENITAL MYOPIA. *World Bulletin of Public Health*. 2024;33:98-100.
13. S.A.Boboev, Boboev SS, Khamrakulov SB, Abdullaeva DA. EFFICACY AND SAFETY OF DIODE-LASER TRANSSCLERAL CYCLOPHOTOCOAGULATION IN THE TREATMENT OF REFRACTORY GLAUCOMA. *World Bulletin of Public Health*. 2022;10:35-37.
14. S.a B, S.s B, S K, D.r A. Micropulse Transscleral Cyclophotocoagulation in Combination with Anti-Vegf Therapy in Patients with Neovascular Glaucoma. *International Journal of Alternative and Contemporary Therapy*. 2024;2(5):149-155.
15. Tolibovich AA, Alimjanovich RJ, Abduazizovich YA, Shavkatjonovna XM. OFTALMOLOGIK YORDAM XOLATI VA UNI DIABETIK RETINOPATIYA BILAN KASALLANGAN BEMORLARDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH (ADABIYOT SHARHI). *JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE*. 2023;8(4). Accessed February 2, 2025. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8258>
16. Kadirova A, Boboev S, Khamidova F, Sobirova D, Khamrakulov S. PERIPHERAL PREVENTIVE LASER COAGULATION OF THE RETINA IN PATIENTS WITH HIGH DEGREE MYOPIA. *Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences*. 2023;10(2S):3932-3940. doi:10.17762/sfs.v10i2S.1716

17. Erkinovich KR. SURGICAL TREATMENT OF JOINT HORIZONTAL STRABISMUS. *World Bulletin of Public Health*. 2022;10:173-178.
18. А.х С, И.б М, Б.п Н, М.э Б, Ж.а Р, Б.а Я. СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОМ ЛЕЧЕНИИ ОСТРОГО КАЛЬКУЛЕЗНОГО ХОЛЕЦИСТИТА. *Research Focus*. 2024;3(3):130-138.
19. Sabirdjanovna KN, O'g'li VSA, Baxtiyorovich MB, O'g'li MBG, O'g'li PLU, Dilorom O. Development of Sarcoidosis after Successful Treatment of Itsenko–Cushing's Disease. *JSML*. 2024;2(5):91-98.
20. Aramovna DZ, Samariddin A, Bobir A, Abbos B, Ravza D. DIAGNOSIS AND INTENSIVE TREATMENT OF TYPE 2 DIABETES TO ACHIEVE THE TARGET LEVEL OF GLYCED HEMOGLOBIN AND REDUCE THE RISK OF VASCULAR COMPLICATIONS. *Research and Implementation*. 2024;2(4):26-35.
21. K.z A, J.a R, Sh.T A. DIAGNOSTIC AND PROGNOSTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF GINGIVAL FLUID CYTOKINES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASES. *TAJMSPR*. 2024;6(07):12-18. doi:10.37547/TAJMSPR/Volume06Issue07-03
22. Aramovna DZ, Suhrob R, Zuhraxon O, Dilovar Z, Muxlisa X, Dilorom O. DIAGNOSTIC AND TREATMENT METHODS OF HYPERPARATHYROIDIS. *FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA JURNALI | JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION, CULTURE AND INNOVATION*. 2024;3(6):1-9.
23. Sabirdjanovna KN, O'g'li RST, O'g'li XHA, Qizi QMM, O'g'li XBU, Qizi TSR. Diagnostic Aspects and Comparative Diagnostics of Thyroid Disease. *JSML*. 2024;2(5):99-106.
24. Rodrigues P, Rizaev JA, Hjadi A, et al. Dual role of microRNA-31 in human cancers; focusing on cancer pathogenesis and signaling pathways. *Experimental Cell Research*. 2024;442(2):114236. doi:10.1016/j.yexcr.2024.114236
25. Daminov AT, Abilov SB ugli, Akhadov AA ugli, Yangabayev SG ugli, Kuchkarova MZ kizi. EFFECT OF NON-STEROID ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUGS IN THE TREATMENT OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS. *FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA*. 2024;3(8):36-40.
26. Saadh MJ, Khalifehsoltani A, Hussein AHA, et al. Exosomal microRNAs in cancer metastasis: A bridge between tumor micro and macroenvironment. *Pathology - Research and Practice*. 2024;263:155666. doi:10.1016/j.prp.2024.155666
27. Rizaev JA, Nazarova NS, Vohidov ER. HOMILADOR AYOLLARDA PARODONT KASALLIKLARI RIVOJLANISHINING PATOGENETIK JIHATLARI. *Журнал гуманитарных и естественных наук*. 2024;(11 [2]):104-107.

28. Djurayeva ZA, Rajabov L rustam o'g'li, Ibragimov A akmal o'g'li, Toshpulatov A yusuf o'g'li, Shomurodov L akobir o'g'li. HOMILADOR AYOLLARNING YENGIL YOD TANQISLIGI VA QALQONSIMON BEZ HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH. *Analysis of world scientific views International Scientific Journal*. 2023;1(8):159-173.
29. Aramovna DZ, Diyorbek K, Diyorjon S, Akrom E, Feruz E, Dilorom O. IODINE DEFICIENCY CONDITIONS. *PEDAGOGIKA, PSIXOLOGIYA VA IJTIMOIIY TADQIQOTLAR/ JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGY, PSYCHOLOGY AND SOCIAL RESEARCH*. 2024;3(5):296-306.
30. Ахматов А, Ахматова ЮА. БЕЛКОВЫЙ МЕТАБОЛИЗМ И ПАТОГЕНЕТИЧЕСКАЯ РОЛЬ ЭНДОГЕННОЙ ИНТОКСИКАЦИИ ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОМ ТУБУЛОИНТЕРСТИЦИАЛЬНОМ НЕФРИТЕ У ДЕТЕЙ. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):603-612.
31. Собирова ДШ, Закирова ЗШ кизи, Гаффорова ЧЕ кизи, Нормаматова ДФ, Эркинова НШ кизи. ГЕСТАЦИОННЫЙ САХАРНЫЙ ДИАБЕТ. *World of Scientific news in Science*. 2024;2(1):607-618.
32. Шухратовна НГ, Суратзода ЗМУХТЗ угли СМ, Шухратовна СД. ГОРМОНАЛЬНАЯ РЕГУЛЯЦИЯ. *Multidisciplinary and Multidimensional Journal*. 2024;3(2):9-18.
33. А.х С, И.б М, Б.п Н, М.э Б. ДИАГНОСТИКА И ЛЕЧЕНИЕ ТЕРМОИНГАЛЯЦИОННОЙ ТРАВМЫ. *Research Focus*. 2024;3(3):120-129.
34. Гульмухамедов ПБ, Ризаев ЖА, Хабилов НЛ, Бобоев КТ. ИЗУЧЕНИЕ УЧАСТИЯ ПОЛИМОРФНОГО ВАРИАНТА ГЕНА MTR (A2756G) В МЕХАНИЗМАХ РАЗВИТИЯ ВРОЖДЕННЫХ ПОРОКОВ ЧЕЛЮСТНО-ЛИЦЕВОЙ ОБЛАСТИ. *INTELLECTUAL EDUCATION TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS AND INNOVATIVE DIGITAL TOOLS*. 2024;3(31):64-68.
35. А.к Х, С.б Ш, С.д К, И.б М. НЕРЕШЕННЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЕ БОЛЬНЫХ С ИНГАЛЯЦИОННЫМИ ТРАВМАМИ. *Boffin Academy*. 2024;2(1):64-74.
36. А.к Х, С.б Ш, Н.к С, И.б М. ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ МЕТОДОВ ИНТЕНСИВНОЙ ТЕРАПИИ ПРИ ОЖОГОВОМ ШОКЕ. *JTCOS*. 2024;6(1):27-39.
37. А.к Х, С.б Ш, И.а Т, И.б М. ПОВРЕЖДЕНИЯ КИШЕЧНИКА ПРИ СОЧЕТАННОЙ ТРАВМЕ ЖИВОТА (Обзор литературы). *Science and innovation*. 2024;4(1):24-35.
38. Гульмухамедов ПБ, Ризаев ЖА, Бобоев КТ, Хабилов НЛ. ПОЛИМОРФИЗМ ГЕНА MTHFR (A1298C) И ВРОЖДЕННЫЕ ПОРОКИ ЧЕЛЮСТНО-

- ЛИЦЕВОЙ ОБЛАСТИ. *INTELLECTUAL EDUCATION TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS AND INNOVATIVE DIGITAL TOOLS*. 2024;3(31):69-73.
39. Алиярович ХА, Бойназарович МИ. ПРИЧИНЫ ПАРАПРОТЕЗНЫХ РЕЦИДИВНЫХ ВЕНТРАЛЬНЫХ ГРЫЖ И ВЫБОР СПОСОБА ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*. 2024;4(11):161-168.
40. Бойназарович МИ, Алиярович ХА. ПРИЧИНЫ РЕЦИДИВА ГРЫЖИ ПОСЛЕ ГЕРНИОАЛЛОПЛАСТИКИ. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*. 2024;4(11):156-160.
41. Ахматов А, Ахматова ЮА. СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ДИАГНОСТИКЕ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО ТУБУЛОИНТЕРСТИЦИАЛЬНОГО НЕФРИТА У ДЕТЕЙ. *Центральноазиатский журнал междисциплинарных исследований и исследований в области управления*. 2024;1(9):65-77.
42. Аблакуловна АЮ, Аблокул А. СОСТОЯНИЕ БЕЛКОВОГО ОБМЕНА И ПАТОГЕНЕТИЧЕСКОЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ЭНДОГЕННОЙ ИНТОКСИКАЦИИ У ДЕТЕЙ С ХРОНИЧЕСКИМ ТУБУЛОИНТЕРСТИЦИАЛЬНЫМ НЕФРИТОМ. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*. 2024;4(5-2):97-107.
43. Hsu CY, Rizaev JA, Pallathadka H, et al. A review of new emerging biosensors based on bacteria-imprinted polymers towards pathogenic bacteria: Promising new tools for selective detection. *Microchemical Journal*. 2024;207:111918. doi:10.1016/j.microc.2024.111918
44. Rizaev JA, Sattorov BB ugli, Nazarova NS. ANALYSIS OF THE SCIENTIFIC BASIS FOR ORGANIZING DENTAL CARE FOR WORKERS IN CONTACT WITH EPOXY RESIN. *Журнал гуманитарных и естественных наук*. 2024;(15):280-283.
45. Sobirdjanovna KN, Abdumaruf A, Tolib B, Shavkat I, Dilorom O. Assessment of the Level of Knowledge of Residents of Samarkand Region about Osteoporosis. *JSML*. 2024;2(4):45-49.
46. Siddikovna TG, Davranovna A, Shuxratovna NG. Basic Mechanisms of Development, Diagnosis and Treatment of Acromegaly. *International Journal of Alternative and Contemporary Therapy*. 2024;2(4):26-29.